

**THE APPLICABILITY OF PLASTIC WASTE AS STRENGTH MODIFIER IN
ASPHALT FOR SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENT**

BY

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the requirements for the award of Master degree in Water Resources and
Environmental Engineering.**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this Dissertation has been written by me and is a record of my own research work. It has not been presented in any previous application for a higher degree of this or any other University. All citations and sources of information are clearly acknowledged by means of reference.

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CERTIFICATION

This dissertation entitled “The Applicability of Plastic Waste as Strength Modifier in Asphalt for Sustainable Environment” by O. O. Adekoya, meets the regulation governing the award of the degree of Master of Engineering of the Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta and is approved for its contribution to scientific knowledge and literary presentation.

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ABSTRACT

The amount of plastic waste generated in the environment is increasing daily, due to human activities such as population increase, socio-economic activities, industrialization, and lifestyle changes. Plastic usage in packaging and bottling has been deployed in every facet of life and the resultant environmental challenges have therefore prompted extensive research to find a lasting solution to the menace. Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE) and Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) are sachet water packs and table water bottles respectively. The extent of use of these materials in the society today and the waste thus generated are enormous. This research work studied the applicability of LDPE and PET waste as strength modifiers in asphaltic road construction. Coarse aggregate and bitumen properties like specific gravity, penetration, flash and fire point tests were determined using standard procedures. The Optimum Binder Content (OBC) of the unmodified asphalt mix was determined using Marshal test method and the resultant mix was used as the control. The PET and LDPE wastes collected were thoroughly washed in water, allowed to dry naturally, shredded and used in sample preparation. The bitumen within the determined OBC was replaced with PET and LDPE waste in the proportion 1, 3 and 5%. Another set of samples were produced with the addition of 1, 3 and 5% of PET and LDPE wastes respectively while the OBC was fixed. Samples were subjected to Marshall Stability (MS) and Marshall Flow (MF) tests. Bulk Density (BD), Void in Total Mix (VTM), and Void Filled with Bitumen (VFB) were all determined for both modified and unmodified asphalt concrete mix produced. Cost analysis was also carried out to determine the cost implication of this modification. The Optimum Binder Content (OBC) was found to be 6.60% by weight of aggregates with MS, MF, BD, VTM, and

VFB being 16.95kN, 4.20mm, 2.37kg/m³, 3.50%, and 81.25% respectively. The maximum LDPE content acceptable was found to be 1% replacement of OBC by weight of aggregate with BD, VTM, VFB, MF, and MS of 2.39kg/m³, 4.06%, 81.25%, 3.82mm and 27.75kN respectively. All the parameters observed for these samples were within the Federal Ministry of Works (FMW) acceptable range. The maximum PET content acceptable was also found to be 1% addition to OBC by weight of aggregate indicating 15% by weight of bitumen with BD, VTM, VFB, MF, and MS being 2.38kg/m³, 3.33%, 82.20%, 4.00 mm and 17.01kN respectively. All the parameters observed for these samples were also within the FMW acceptable range. The cost analysis shows a 7.37% cost reduction in the case of LDPE waste and a 0.90% cost increase in the case of PET waste. The plastic waste modified asphalt forms better material for pavement construction and so reduces the quantity of plastic waste in our environment.

DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to God Almighty for His ever – available help through all the stages of this work.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Plastic is a very versatile material. Due to the industrial revolution, and its large scale production plastic seemed to be a cheaper and effective raw material; it is therefore tagged as a friend of the common man (Amit *et al.*, 2012). Today, every vital sector of the economy starting from agriculture to packaging, automobile, electronics, electrical, building construction, communication sectors has been virtually revolutionized by the applications of plastics. Plastic are non-biodegradable material and researchers have found that the material can remain on earth for 4500 years without degradation (Amit *et al.*, 2012). Encyclopaedia of Polymer Science and Technology (1992) said it is because they are made of large molecules, formed by the union of identical monomers which may be natural (Cellulose or DNA), or synthetic (nylon or polyethylene). It is therefore a problem to the environment after its use. The world consumption of plastic is estimated to between 24 kg to 28 kg per capita per year with only 25 % of this waste being recycled (Amit *et al.*, 2012). Due to the change in scenario of life style, the demand is increasing everyday across the globe. Sinan *et al.* (2008) said if this trend continues, in the next few decades the earth will be buried under a pile of disposable plastic material and the soil will be non-cultivable and the globe will turn into a ball with a plastic layer.

In Nigeria, this pocket friendly and environmentally hazardous material 'plastic' has found its root in our portable water supply industry. The provision of an adequate supply of safe drinking water was one of the eight components of primary health care identified by the International conference on primary health care in 1978. Increase in human population has exerted an enormous pressure on the provision of safe drinking

water especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Before independence in Nigeria, water was supplied to the public by the government free of charge. Today, Nigeria has moved from being a mixed economy to capitalist economy, in cities and towns today, water now attracts rates and fees (Sangodoyin, 1990). With insufficient government supply of water, private sector participation has evolved and the idea of packaging portable drinking water referred to as 'pure water' is now a common phenomenon in Nigeria. Drinking water is now commercially packed in easy-to-open 50 – 60 ml polyethylene sacs and bottles and are referred to as “sachet or pure water and bottled water” respectively (Edema *et al.*, 2011).

Water sachets and bottles are made of low density polyethylene (LDPE) and Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) materials respectively. They are very cheap, strong and therefore, attracting patronage from the low to middle strata of the populace. These plastic wastes are dumped indiscriminately and therefore constitute huge environmental menace. The challenges posed are overwhelming not only due to their non-biodegradable nature, but also by their large volume per unit mass. Panda *et al.* (2009) reported that plastics in municipal waste streams make up only 7 – 9 % of the weight of the total waste stream; by volume they may represent 20-30 %. However, the alarming thing is that most countries of the world do not have efficient means of managing this volume of plastic waste according to Panda *et al.* (2009) and Nigeria happens to be one of such countries. Government at all levels of governance in Nigeria today are faced with this huge task of nylon and plastic waste management, used pure water sachets and table water bottles are common eye-sour in our streets, drainages are thereby impeded, and this affects the free flow of water channels and canals. Huge sums of money are expended by government at all tiers to construct new roads, drainage channels and canals but the menace of waste nylon and plastics have

caused more harm than good to the roads. The economic and environmental impacts of this plastic waste is increasing significantly as they clog domestic sewage systems, choking water drains, threatening aquatic life in receiving water systems, often causing soil degradation, reducing biodiversity and the aesthetic quality of city parks and beaches (Adewumi, 2006).

These wastes breed mosquitoes causing malaria and other related diseases. Environmentalists are seriously worried with this development and the best way out is been researched daily and Health workers are also working day and night to find cures for different ailments caused by this environmental menace.

Making use of these waste materials as a modifier in asphalt mixtures is among the methods proposed for mitigating their associated environmental damages. This is because several million tons of asphalt is used for road pavement every year. Then asphalt pavement seems to be a good opportunity for using a lot of these wastes as a way to recycle, reuse and reduce plastic waste. This also enhances public perception of this waste as useful raw materials, create buoyant markets and therefore reduce disposal of industrial wastes to landfill. There is a need to demonstrate where these materials can offer real benefits over their primary alternatives, e.g. as aggregates. By emphasizing the “added value” that it may bring to asphalt, these materials may be placed in an advantageous market position.

1.1 Problem Statement

Nigeria is 923,768 Km² in total landmass and from his research calculations David (2012) said that the country generates approximately about 990,344 Km² (area) of sachet water waste daily which is larger than the total landmass of the country.

The resultant effects of this indiscriminate dumping of plastic wastes according to this researcher includes an increase in disease transmission; because these plastics are non-biodegradable they tend to store water and the stored water act as breeding place for insects e.g. mosquitoes which transmit malaria

They contaminate ground and surface water by affecting aquatic lives when dumped in rivers or water bodies by limiting the penetration of sunlight and diffusion of oxygen. When dumped on the ground surface they do not allow plants to grow there by reducing the area of land for agriculture.

Burning of these wastes generates greenhouse gas emissions and other air pollutants like carbon monoxide, soot and nitrogen oxide, all of which are hazardous to human health and degrades urban air quality. Combustion of Polyvinyl Chlorides (PVC) generates highly carcinogenic dioxins (David, 2012).

When solid wastes are dumped into rivers or streams it can alter aquatic habitats and harm native plants and animals and affects biodiversity thereby damaging the ecosystem. Furthermore, the accumulation of these wastes along streets may cause physical hazards; clog drainage channels, canals and so causing localized flooding.

In time past, several methods for disposal of this waste have been attempted; namely landfill, incineration, chemical recovery, true material recycling, etc. Decrease in landfill availability and increase cost are some of the factors rendering land filling unacceptable. Incineration of plastic wastes, like water sachet and table water bottled, results in environmental danger due to the emissions of various combustion products as described above. True material recycling among others which entail converting the waste into products that can be reused is found to reduce cost of disposal according to Usman *et al.*, (2012).

Recycling of plastic wastes to produce reusable plastics and bags is one of the ways by which efforts is been made to tackle this environmental menace in Nigeria. Lagos State government of Nigeria has already undertaken a plastic waste recycling project at the Olushosun waste dump site by constructing a plastic waste recycling plant on the dump site. Considering short span of the cycle of this type of recycling process as well as the inadequacy of such plant across the country, it becomes necessary to further find ways to complement this effort.

This study therefore intend to investigate one of the true material recycling methods which involve the possibility of utilizing plastics wastes in road construction, thereby probably reducing the cost of road construction and making the environment safe for living.

1.2 Justification for the Study.

Going by the current problems in recycling of plastic waste worldwide and their accumulation in landfill sites as well as the carcinogenic nature of these substances all of these coupled with the fact that asphalt pavements are considered as national capital and each year much of the country's development budget is spent on road pavements, maintenance and improvement, a well defined study to investigate the possibility of using these wastes in order to reduce environmental problems in recycling and burial of these materials in landfills is needful.

1.3 Aim of the study

The aim of this study was to investigate the possibility of using Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE) and Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) wastes in asphalt production as a measure to safely dispose plastic wastes and thereby reduce associated environmental problems.

1.3.1 Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study were to:

- i. determine the optimum binder content of the grade of bitumen (60/70) to be used for this research.
- ii. analyze the effect of this plastic modifications on technical characteristics of asphalt.
- iii. determine the percentage cost difference resulting from the modification.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Plastic in the Environment

The accelerated growth of urban population with unplanned urbanization, increasing economic activities and lack of training in modern solid waste management practices in developing countries complicates the efforts to improve solid waste services. The changes in consumption patterns with alterations in the waste characteristics have also resulted in a quantum jump in solid waste generation (Ludwig *et al.*, 2003). The quantum of plastic waste in Municipal Solid Waste (see Plates 1, 2, 3 & 4) is increasing due to increase in population, urbanization, development activities and changes in life style, which is leading to widespread littering on the landscape. Thus disposal of waste plastic is a menace and is becoming a serious problem globally due to their non-biodegradability and unaesthetic view according to (Ludwig *et al.*, 2003). The world is facing a waste crisis from the plastics produced today: Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE), High Density Polyethylene (HDPE), Polypropylene (PP), Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), etc. World production of PVC today is at more than 20 million tonnes per year – up from 3 million tonnes in 1965 (Greenpeace, 2011.) Currently, plastic wastes contribute more than 65% of the municipal solid waste in Nigeria, with food and paper waste making up the rest (Globe Net Market Report, 2005).

If we are to achieve sustainable development, we will need to display greater responsibility for the ecosystems on which all life depends, for each other as a single human community, and for the generations that will follow our own, living tomorrow

with the consequences of the decisions we take today. (Indian Centre for Plastics in the Environment ICPE, 2011).

2.2. The 3Rs concept in plastic waste management

The 3Rs concept is simply;

- Reduce,
- Reuse and
- Recycle

2.2.1. Reduce

This is aimed at avoiding waste, looking for ways to produce and use goods that stop waste being generated and reducing waste. Choosing products that can be used productively, recycled locally, and have minimal packaging (Eisenberg, 2011). Retailers and consumers can select products that use little or no packaging or select packaging materials that are recycled into new packaging. If people refuse plastic as a packaging material, the industry will decrease production for that purpose, and the associated problems such as energy use, pollution, and adverse health effects will diminish (MDNR, 2013). Consider buying loose fruit and vegetables rather than pre-packaged and using reusable bags when shopping.

2.2.2. Reuse

Reuse involves the repeated use of items or parts of items which still have usable aspects. Since refillable plastic containers can be reused for many times, container reuse can lead to a substantial reduction in the demand for disposable plastic and reduced use of materials and energy, with the consequent reduced environmental impacts (MDNR, 2013). Container designers will take into account the fate of the container beyond the point of sale and consider the service the container provides.

Reuse drink bottles for outings or storage and reuse plastic bags as bin liners or for shopping.

2.2.3. Recycle

Recycling means the use of waste itself as resources. Eisenberg (2011) classified Plastic Waste can be recycled in the following ways:

- (i) Plastic process scrap recycling – this are polymers left over from the production of plastics. They are relatively simple and economical to recycle, as there is a regular and reliable source and the material is relatively uncontaminated. This is usually described as reprocessing rather than recycling.
- (ii) Post-use plastic recycling – Post-use plastic can be described as plastic material arising from products that have undergone a first full service life prior to being recovered. Households are the biggest source of plastic waste, but recycling household plastics presents a number of challenges. One of these relates to collection.
- (iii) Mechanical recycling - Mechanical recycling of plastics refers to processes which involve the melting, shredding or granulation of waste plastics. Plastics must be sorted prior to mechanical recycling. Mostly, sorting is done manually. Following sorting, the plastic is either melted down directly and molded into a new shape, or melted down after being shredded into flakes and then processed into granules called re-granulate.
- (iv) Chemical or feedstock recycling – Feedstock recycling describes a range of plastic recovery techniques to make plastics, which break down polymers into their constituent monomers, which in turn can be used again in refineries, or petrochemical and chemical production. A range of feedstock recycling

technologies is currently being explored. These include: (i) Pyrolysis, (ii) Hydrogenation, (iii) Gasification and (iv) Thermal cracking.

The concept of minimizing waste impacts in terms of quantity, by reducing quantity of wastes, reusing the waste products with simple treatments and recycling the wastes by using it as resources to produce same or modified products is usually referred to as 3Rs (Eisenberg, 2011). Purchasing and using resources with care can reduce the pace of consumption of resources and ultimately reducing wastes multifold for waste streams. When long lasting goods are reused time and again, it offsets harvesting of new similar or same products. This saves fresh resources exploitation and waste generation quantity (Eisenberg, 2011). Some waste products can be consumed as resources for production of different goods or the same product, meaning recycling the same resource. This too saves fresh resources and offsets waste generation. All in all, the 3Rs individually or collectively saves fresh resources exploitation, add value to the already exploited resources and very importantly minimizes the waste quantity and its ill effects. Waste minimization efficiency is stated to be better achieved applying 3Rs in a hierarchical order- Reduce, Reuse and Recycle (Eisenberg, 2011; MDNR, 2013)

2.3 Strategies and Legislations to promote 3Rs concept in some selected Countries

2.3.1 Hong Kong approach

Hong Kong's Product Eco-responsibility Ordinance (Cap. 603) for example was enacted in July 2008. The Ordinance is a piece of "framework" legislation that provides a legal basis for implementing producer responsibility schemes in the country. The environmental levy scheme on plastic shopping bags (the Levy Scheme) is the first scheme to be implemented under the Ordinance (Hong Kong Special Administrative Region 2008)

According to the ordinance the objective of the Levy Scheme is to provide a direct economic incentive to encourage the public to switch to reusable shopping bags with a view to reducing the indiscriminate use of plastic shopping bags. The Product Eco-responsibility (Plastic Shopping Bags) Regulation (the Regulation) which sets out the implementation details of the Levy Scheme was approved by the Legislative Council on 23 April 2009. The commencement notices for both the Ordinance and Regulation have been posted on Gazette published on 30 April 2009.

The Levy Scheme came into operation on 7 July 2009. Under the Levy Scheme, registered retailers are no longer allowed to provide free plastic shopping bags; and they must charge their customers an environmental levy for each plastic shopping bag they ask for.

To ensure a successful introduction and an effective administration, the Levy Scheme adopts a phased approach by first covering chain or large retailers. Typical examples include supermarkets, convenience stores, personal health and beauty stores, drug stores, department stores, etc.

Under the Levy Scheme, prescribed retailers shall register their qualified retail outlets as registered retail outlets, otherwise no plastic shopping bag shall be provided from these qualified retail outlets. Retailers who have successfully registered under the Levy Scheme would become registered retailers and they will:

- have a certificate of registration displayed at each of their registered retail outlets; and
- display tent cards and stickers bearing the Levy Scheme's logo.

Prescribed Retailer; is a person who carries on a retail business at -

- 5 or more qualified retail outlets in Hong Kong; or

- at least one qualified retail outlet in Hong Kong that has a retail floor area of not less than 200 m².

Qualified Retail Outlet; A "qualified retail outlet" under this scheme is one that offers all of the following categories of goods for sale-

- any food or drink;
- any medicine or first-aid item; and
- any personal hygiene or beauty product.

The Levy: The environmental levy is set at 50 cents for each plastic shopping bag given out at a registered retail outlet. This level is based on public opinion survey as well as previous voluntary campaigns which indicated that a levy of 50 cents would create sufficient incentive to reduce the use of plastic shopping bags on the one hand, but not exceeding a level generally accepted by the public on the other.

The introduction of the environmental levy was considered to help change the public's habit and lead to a sustained reduction in the use of plastic shopping bags in Hong Kong.

2.3.2 Indian Plastic Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2011:

Gazette of India Extraordinary {Part II Sec. 3(ii)}

On February 7th, 2011, the Indian Ministry of Environment and Forests in press release notified the public of the Plastic Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2011 to replace the earlier Recycled Plastics Manufacture and Usage Rules, 1999 (amended in 2003).

From the Minister for Environment and Forests, Mr. Jairam Ramesh said "It is impractical and undesirable to impose a blanket ban on the use of plastic all over the country. The real challenge is to improve municipal solid waste management systems. In addition to the privatization and mechanization of the municipal solid waste

management systems we must be sensitive to the needs and concerns of the lakhs of people involved in the informal sector” (Shuddham, 2011).

Some of the salient features of the new Rules according to Gazette of India Extraordinary {Part II Sec. 3(ii)} 2011 are:-

- (i) Use of plastic materials in sachets for storing, packing or selling gutkha, tobacco and pan masala has been banned.
- (ii) Under the new Rules, foodstuffs will not be allowed to be packed in recycled plastics or compostable plastics.
- (iii) Recycled carry bags shall conform to specific BIS standards.
- (iv) Plastic carry bags shall either be white or only with those pigments and colourants which are in conformity with the bar prescribed by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS). This shall apply expressly for pigments and colourants to be used in plastic products which come in contact with foodstuffs, pharmaceuticals and drinking water.
- (v) Plastic carry bags shall not be less than 40 microns in thickness. Under the earlier Rules, the minimum thickness was 20 microns. Several State Governments in the meanwhile, had stipulated varying minimum thickness. It is now expected that 40 microns norms will become the uniform standard to be followed across the country.
- (vi) The minimum size (of 8×12 inches) for the plastic carry bags prescribed under the earlier Rules has been dispensed with.
- (vii) Carry bags can be made from compostable plastics provided they conform to BIS standards.

One of the major provisions under the new Rules is the explicit recognition of the role of waste pickers. The new Rules require the municipal authority to constructively

engage agencies or groups working in waste management including these waste pickers (Shuddham, 2011).

Additional Safeguards:

- No carry bags shall be made available free of cost to consumers. The municipal authority may determine the minimum price for plastic carry bags.
- The municipal authority may also direct the manufacturers to establish plastic waste collection centers, either collectively or individually, in line with the principle of 'Extended Producers Responsibility'.
- The Rules have stipulated provisions for marking or labeling to indicate name, registration number of the manufacturer, thickness and also to indicate whether they are recycled or compostable.

2.3.3 Japan's Container and Packaging Recycling Law:

Fully (passed June 1995, partial entry into force April 1997, full entry 2000, amended 2006)

The aim of the Containers and Packaging Recycling Law is to reduce the amount of garbage generated, by promoting more effective use of resources in containers and packaging waste, which accounts for about 60 % of household waste (by volume) according to the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry. The basic principle of this law is that every player has a role to play in recycling. Consumers should separate their waste according to category, municipalities should collect the separated waste, and businesses should recycle what has been collected into new products (METI, 2006).

2.3.4 Ireland Waste Management Regulations

The Waste Management (Environmental Levy) (Plastic Bag) (Amendment) Regulations 2007 (S.I. No. 66 of 2007) revoked and provides for an increase in the

amount of the levy on plastic bags from 15 cent to 22 cent per bag with effect from 1 July 2007 (Ministry for the Environment, Heritage and Local Government, 2007).

The Waste Management (Landfill levy) (Amendment) Regulations 2013 (S.I. No. 194 of 2013) increase the landfill levy for waste disposed of an authorized and unauthorized landfill facilities from €65 per tonne to €75 per tonne with effect from 1 July 2013. (Ministry for the Environment, Heritage and Local Government, 2013).

2.3.5 County of Hawaii's Plastic Bag Reduction Ordinance

The purpose of the ordinance is to reduce or eliminate single use plastic carryout bags. The law became effective January 17, 2013 and Hawai'i is the first state to have plastic bag reduction laws in all counties. Important information about the new laws is:

All County of Hawaii's businesses including groceries, restaurants, farmer's markets and other retailers must comply. Beginning January 17, 2013, if stores provided single use plastic carryout bags, they were required to charge a fee. Starting on January 17, 2014, all single-use plastic carryout bags are prohibited. The Ordinance allows for plastic bags to be used for bulk items such as meat, fish, nuts, grains, fresh produce, small hardware, garments & prescription drugs (County of Hawai'i, 2005).

2.4 Research Works on Possible Application (Recycling) of Plastic Waste

2.4.1 Plastics Waste Disposal through Plasma Pyrolysis Technology (PPT)

Plasma Pyrolysis is a technology, which integrates the thermochemical properties of plasma with the pyrolysis process according to the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) of India (CPCB, 2013). The intense and versatile heat generation capabilities of PPT enables it to dispose off all types of plastic wastes including polymeric, biomedical and hazardous waste in a safe and reliable manner.

In plasma pyrolysis, firstly the plastics waste is fed into the primary chamber at 8500 °C through a feeder. The waste material dissociates into carbon monoxide, hydrogen, methane, higher hydrocarbons etc. Induced draft fan drains the pyrolysis gases as well as plastics waste into the secondary chamber, where these gases are combusted in the presence of excess air. The inflammable gases are ignited with high voltage spark. The secondary chamber temperature is maintained at around 10500 °C. The hydrocarbon, carbon monoxide and hydrogen are combusted into safe carbon dioxide and water. The process conditions are maintained so that it eliminates the possibility of formation of toxic dioxins and furans molecules (in case of chlorinated waste). The conversion of organic waste into non toxic gases (CO₂, H₂O) is more than 99 % according to CPCB. The extreme conditions of Plasma kill stable bacteria such as *Bacillus stereothermophilus* and *Bacillus subtilis* immediately. Segregation of the waste is not necessary, as very high temperatures ensure treatment of all types of waste without discrimination (CPCB, 2013)

Students at Northeastern University have developed a device that converts plastic to electricity (Mahony, 2010). The waste combustor processes non-recyclable plastic within two tanks. The top tank converts the plastic to gas through pyrolysis and the gas then travels to a lower tank, where it is burned to generate heat and steam. The steam powers a turbine to produce electricity.

Leader of the research project is Prof. Yiannis Levendis, a Professor of Mechanical Engineering is examining ways to tweak the vaporization of plastic in order to reduce any harmful emissions that are released when burning the resulting gas (Mahony, 2010).

According to the researchers, the combustor could be scaled up for use in a power plant. Ideally, with a recycling plant just next door. This would obviously take a lot of

infrastructure adjustment. But with the speed at which plastic biodegrades, we have a lot of time.

2.4.2 Conversion of plastics waste into Liquid Fuel

A research-cum-demonstration plant was set up at Nagpur, Maharashtra for conversion of waste plastics into liquid fuel. The process adopted is based on random de-polymerization of waste plastics into liquid fuel in presence of a catalyst. The entire process is undertaken in closed reactor vessel followed by condensation, if required. Waste plastics while heating up to 2700 °C to 3000 °C convert into liquid-vapour state, which is collected in condensation chamber in the form of liquid fuel while the tarry liquid waste is topped-down from the heating reactor vessel. The organic gas is generated which is vented due to lack of storage facility. However, the gas can be used in dual fuel diesel-generator set for generation of electricity.

Moinuddin *et al.* (2011) research, described a process to convert solid waste plastics into renewable energy sources accomplished using a basic form of thermal degradation. The final product (Natural State Research- NSR, NSR-1, and NSR-2 fuels) obtained from the process is in the form of liquid and it contains hydrocarbon materials.

NSR-1 and gasoline were injected into the gasoline generator one after the other to compare the kilowatt output of the two. The results showed a significantly higher kilowatt output from NSR-1 than gasoline.

When these fuels were tested according to the American Standard for Testing Materials (ASTM) methods and tests were also performed by a third party certified laboratory (INTERTEK, NJ) and the results show that a very considerate amount of harmful compounds are present in the NSR fuels.

2.4.3 Application of waste plastic in concreting

Baboo *et al.*, (2012), studied a number of concrete mixes in which sand was partially replaced by waste plastic flakes in varying percentages by volume. Waste plastic mix concrete with and without superplasticizer was tested at room temperature. Cube samples were molded for compressive strength tests at three, seven, and twenty-eight days. Beams were also cast to study the flexural strength characteristic of waste plastic mix concrete. It was found that the reduction in workability and compressive strength, due to partially replacement of sand by waste plastic, is minimal and can be enhanced by addition of super plasticizer.

Bhogayata *et al.*, (2013), studied plastic waste known as metalized polythene in macro pellet form added to the conventional concrete to study the changes in the basic strength properties. A conventional concrete with 0.45 water/cement ratio was prepared and plastic pellets were added by 0.5 %, 1 % and 1.5 % by concrete volume. Compressive strength, split tensile strength and surface tensile test were performed on the samples. The test results revealed the reduction of strength properties up to 60 %. It could be observed that the plastic beyond 1.5 % proportion could make the concrete not suitable for construction work except where the lean concrete could be used.

Another innovation in this area is the Lightweight aggregate for concrete from recycling of plastic waste (NUMIX 2012) project which is aimed at the establishment of business partnerships among European industries, working in plastic recycling and in concrete manufacturing. The purpose is to involve:

- industries operating in the field of recycled plastic, which will be enabled to produce the recycled aggregates thanks to the results obtained in the project,

- industries operating in the field of concrete manufacturing, which will produce lightened concrete and mortar containing the innovative aggregates,
- industries operating in the field of concrete manufacturing, end-user of the building product containing the innovative aggregates.

The Raw materials are by-products from the sorting of recycled plastics (from solid urban and industrial / craft made / commercial waste): mixed plastic waste (NUMIX 2012). While the Semi-finished and finished products respectively are;

- Expanded granules to be used as aggregate for lightened structural and nonstructural concrete, substituting the expanded clay.
- Densified flakes to be used as aggregate for mortar and as raw material for expanded granules.
- Other products are lightweight concrete and mortar.

All experimental tests evidenced that expanded granules can be a valuable substitute of traditional expanded clay (NUMIX 2012). And the main achievable improvements are:

- weight reduction
- mixing water control
- insulating properties

Partners in this project include:

- Consorzio CETMA - Italy
- DFS Montenegro Engineering - Montenegro
- ACCIONA INFRAESTRUCTURES S.A. - Spain
- Centro Riciclo Vedelago S.r.l. - Italy

- SGI Studio Galli Ingegneria S.p.A. – Italy

2.4.4 Lagos State waste management scheme

In August 1999, Senator Bola Ahmed Tinubu Government in Lagos State launched the waste to wealth programme, it was obviously in response to the terrible state of the environment in the state as at the time. (Chibueze, 2013).

The government of Babatunde Fashola made environmental cleanness a top priority on assumption of office in 2007, his efforts appeared not to be yielding the desired result as the volume of waste kept increasing by the day. The landfill sites were over flowing necessitating the creation of new ones. Knowing that land is a scarce commodity in the state he gave life to the project by empowering the Lagos State Waste Management Authority (LAWMA), the body charged with the responsibility of waste management in the state.

So it was time to look for a solution, a solution that will not only help the state maintain a clean environment and a healthy citizenry, but also save the landfills and create wealth. Mrs. Tolu Adeyo, recycling manager, Olusosun Recycling Plant in an interview said “we could not afford to continue to land fill those waste while there are recyclable materials in there. That is why we are looking at the issue of recycling so that it will prolong the landfills and ensure environmental sustainability. So as much as possible we try to reduce what goes into our landfills (Chibueze, 2013). Lagos State generates over 10,000 metric tonnes of waste daily according to LAWMA. In time past virtually every street had a refuse dump rising as high as a storey building, producing offensive odors and obstructing traffic and in some cases causing flooding as it blocks the drains.

The States Waste To-Wealth programme is an integrated waste management system that involves recycling of solid waste into various new products including clean energy. The project which is being executed by the LAWMA in partnership with the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the African Carbon Asset Development (ACAD) is expected to capture methane gas from waste and use it to generate electricity. The project apart from preventing the release of greenhouse gases which endanger the environment will also create jobs and provide infrastructure through public-private partnership (PPP) among others.

Mr. Ola Oresanya, managing director of LAWMA in an interview explained that the objectives of the project are to fully harness and utilize alternative options available in managing waste, thus reducing reliance on landfill disposal as well as minimize the emission of greenhouse gases, while managing waste in an environmentally sound, socially responsible and financially sustainable manner.

The waste to wealth programme according to Oresanya, also include nylon buyback programme, recycling banks, recycling plant at the Olusosun recycling centre; collection of PET bottles, satchet water packs, among many others. It is instructive to know that this sustainable system environmental management through waste to wealth is catching the attention of other states in the federation. Ondo State has already introduced the system with the slogan: Pure water satchet = Cash (Chibueze, 2013).

2.4.5 Application in Asphalt Road Construction

In the past few years, considerable research has been carried out to determine the suitability of plastic waste modifier in construction of bituminous mixes (Sunil, B. *et al.*, 2004). Zoorab and Suparma (2000) reported the use of recycled plastics composed predominantly of polypropylene and low density polyethylene in plain bituminous

concrete mixtures with increased durability and improved fatigue life. Dense bituminous macadam with recycled plastics, mainly low density polyethylene (LDPE) replacing 30 % of 2.36 – 5 mm aggregates, reduced the mix density by 16% and showed a 250 % increase in Marshall Stability; the indirect tensile strength (ITS) was also improved in the mixtures.

Afroz and Prasad (2012) investigated the potential use of waste plastic as a modifier for asphalt concrete and cement concrete pavement. Different ratios of plastic such as Polypropylene (PP), Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE), and High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) by weight of asphalt were blended with 80 / 100 paving grade asphalt. Unmodified and modified asphalt binders were subjected to rheological test. The performance tests including, Marshall Stability, loss of stability tests were conducted using plastic coated aggregates and polymer modified bitumen on Hot Mix Asphalt (HMA) mixtures. The work was done by using plastic coated aggregates in cement concrete pavements. The results showed better values for asphalt concrete. Then they concluded that this is an eco-friendly process.

In their study, Ambika *et al.* (2012) used PVC pipe waste as a modifier up to a level of 3% and 5% in making bituminous product for paving application. To make a homogeneous blend, waste PVC was initially treated with a chemical and then blended with bitumen. The visco-elastic properties of the bitumen-PVC blend such as storage modulus, loss modulus and phase angle were studied and compared with those of unmodified bitumen. Later the performance characteristics of bituminous mix made up of these modified binders were also studied and compared with those of conventional bituminous mix. The results indicate that PVC pipe waste can be used successfully in road construction. Strength and stability of the mix increased after incorporation of PVC pipe waste, it was also observed that addition of PVC pipe waste showed

increased resistance to permanent deformation in terms of rutting. (Ambika *et al.*, 2012)

Yinusa and Stephen (2011), in their study dissolved pure water sachet in a petroleum by product (Dual Purpose Kerosene- DPK) as a partial replacement of and additions to the optimum bitumen content. The variation of the Marshall Stability, flow and Voids in Total Mix (VTM), Voids Filled with Binder (VFB) and Voids in Mineral Aggregates (VMA) were monitored as the proportion of the emulsified dissolved sachets increased. The respective Marshall Stability values of 1,400 kg for unmodified bitumen binder; 1,150 kg at 15 % partial replacement (1 % dissolved pure water + 5 % optimum bitumen content = 6 % binder) and 1200 kg at 25 % addition (2 % dissolved: pure water + 6 % optimum bitumen content = 8 % binder) were recorded; which were both higher than the desired stability for heavily trafficked pavement.

In their conclusion they said Dissolved Pure Water Sachet can be combined with bitumen to exhibit the desired flow and stability of an HMA wearing or bearing course for a flexible pavement at 15 % replacement of the optimum binder content and 25 % additions by weight of total mix (in emulsified condition). The bitumen modification method of additions to the optimum binder is also said to be more effective for pollution control because of higher demand of the waste, 25 % compared to 15 %.

Olukorede and Kehinde (2012) in their study used shredded sachet of pure water. The bitumen was replaced by shredded waste water sachets by weight at 1 to 10 % and concluded that the property of bitumen was strongly enhanced by the addition of shredded water sachet. The modification was found to enhance the resistance to permanent deformation, fatigue cracking and cohesion and the asphalt cement can be modified with about 1 to 3 % used shredded water sachet. They recommended further

study involving asphalt concrete production with the modified bitumen. This study is therefore to further explore the findings of Olukorede and Kehinde (2012).

2.5 Data on plastic consumption and generation of plastic waste

A material that contains one or more organic polymers of large molecular weight, solid in its finish state and at some state while manufacturing or processing into finished articles, can be shaped by its flow is termed as plastics. The major categories of plastics are;

- Thermoplastics and
- Thermoset plastics.

The thermoplastics, constitute 80 % and thermoset constitutes approximately 20 % of total postconsumer plastics waste generated. The world plastic per capita per year consumption is put at 24 – 28 kg and only 25 % of this is currently recycled world over as shown in Table 1. (Amit *et al.*, 2012).

Table 1: Plastic Waste Consumption

S. No	Description	World
1	Per capita per year consumption of plastic (Kg)	24-28
2	2 Recycling (%)	25
3	Plastic in solid waste (%)	7

Source: Amit *et al.*, (2012)

2.6 Plastic Waste Classification

Plastics can be classified in many ways, but most commonly by their physical properties. Plastics may be classified also according to their chemical sources. The twenty or more known basic types fall into four general groups: Cellulose Plastics, Synthetic Resin Plastics, Protein Plastics, Natural Resins, Elastomers and Fibers. But depending on their physical properties, may be classified as thermoplastic and thermosetting materials. Thermoplastic materials can be formed into desired shapes under heat and pressure and become solids on cooling. If they are subjected to the same conditions of heat and pressure, they can be remolded. Thermosetting materials which once shaped cannot be softened or remolded by the application of heat. The examples of some typical thermoplastic and thermosetting materials are shown on Table 2, while Table 3 shows the sources of some of these plastic wastes.

Table 2: Typical thermoplastic and thermosetting materials

S. No	Thermoplastic	Thermosetting
1.	Polyethylene Teryphthalate (PET)	Bakelite
2.	Polypropylene (PP)	Epoxy
3.	Polyvinyl Acetate (PVA)	Melamine
4.	Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC)	Polyester
5.	Polystyrene (PS)	Polyurethane
6.	Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE)	Urea – Formaldehyde
7.	High Density Polyethylene (HDPE)	Alkyd

Source: (CPCB, 2009)

Most of thermoplastics on heating soften at temperature between 130-140 °C. The Thermal Gravimetric Analysis - TGA analysis of thermoplastics has proven that there is no gas evolution in the temperature range of 130-180 °C and beyond 180 °C gas evolution and thermal degradation may occur. Thus the waste plastic can easily be blended with the bitumen as the process for road construction using bitumen is carried out in the range of 155-165 °C.

Table 3: Types of plastics and usage.

Waste Plastic	Origin
Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE)	Carry bags, sacks, milk pouches, bin lining, cosmetic and detergent bottles.
High Density Polyethylene (HDPE)	Carry bags, bottle caps, house hold articles etc.
Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET)	Drinking water bottles etc.,
Polypropylene (PP)	Bottle caps and closures, wrappers of detergent, biscuit, vapors packets, microwave trays for readymade meal etc.,
Polystyrene (PS)	Yoghurt pots, clear egg packs, bottle caps. Foamed Polystyrene: food trays, egg boxes, disposable cups protective packaging etc
Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC)	Mineral water bottles, credit cards, toys, pipes and gutters; electrical fittings, furniture, folders and pens, medical disposables; etc

Source: Amit *et al.*, (2012)

2.7 Different forms of bitumen

Bitumen is a sticky, black and highly viscous liquid or semi-solid, in some natural deposits. It is also the residue or by-product of fractional distillation of crude petroleum. Bitumen composed primarily of highly condensed polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, containing 95 % carbon and hydrogen (± 87 % carbon and ± 8 % hydrogen), up to 5 % sulfur, 1 % nitrogen, 1 % oxygen and 2000 ppm metals. Also bitumen is mixture of about 300 - 2000 chemical components, with an average of around 500 - 700. It is the heaviest fraction of crude oil, the one with highest boiling point (525 °C). (Amit *et al.*, 2012).

2.7.1 Cutback bitumen

Normal practice is to heat bitumen to reduce its viscosity. In some situations preference is given to use liquid binders such as cutback bitumen. In cutback bitumen suitable solvent is used to lower the viscosity of the bitumen. From the environmental point of view also cutback bitumen is preferred. The solvent from the bituminous material will evaporate and the bitumen will bind the aggregate. Cutback bitumen is used for cold weather bituminous road construction and maintenance. The distillates used for preparation of cutback bitumen are naphtha, kerosene, diesel oil, and furnace oil. There are different types of cutback bitumen like rapid curing (RC), medium curing (MC), and slow curing (SC). RC is recommended for surface dressing and patchwork. MC is recommended for premix with less quantity of fine aggregates. SC is used for premix with appreciable quantity of fine aggregates. (Amit *et al.*, 2012).

2.7.2 Bitumen emulsion

Bitumen emulsion is a liquid product in which bitumen is suspended in a finely divided condition in an aqueous medium and stabilized by suitable material. Normally

cationic type emulsions are used in India. The bitumen content in the emulsion is around 60% and the remaining is water. When the emulsion is applied on the road it breaks down resulting in release of water and the mix starts to set. The time of setting depends upon the grade of bitumen. The viscosity of bituminous emulsions can be measured as per IS: 8887-1995. Three types of bituminous emulsions are available, which are Rapid setting (RS), Medium setting (MS), and Slow setting (SC). Bitumen emulsions are ideal binders for hill road construction. Where heating of bitumen or aggregates are difficult. Rapid setting emulsions are used for surface dressing work. Medium setting emulsions are preferred for premix jobs and patch repairs work. Slow setting emulsions are preferred in rainy season (Amit *et al.*, 2012).

2.7.3 Bituminous primers

In bituminous primer the distillate is absorbed by the road surface on which it is spread. The absorption therefore depends on the porosity of the surface. Bitumen primers are useful on the stabilized surfaces and water bound macadam base courses. Bituminous primers are generally prepared on road sites by mixing penetration bitumen with petroleum distillate (Amit *et al.*, 2012).

2.7.4 Modified bitumen

Certain additives or blend of additives called as bitumen modifiers can improve properties of Bitumen and bituminous mixes. Bitumen treated with these modifiers is known as modified bitumen (Amit *et al.*, 2012). The advantages of using modified bitumen are as follows:

- Lower susceptibility to daily and seasonal temperature variations
- Higher resistance to deformation at high pavement temperature

- Better age resistance properties
- Higher fatigue life for mixes
- Better adhesion between aggregates and binder
- Prevention of cracking and reflective cracking

2.7.5 Various grades of bitumen used for pavement purpose

The various grades of bitumen use in asphalt road construction include the following:

- Grade 30 / 40
- Grade 60 / 70
- Grade 80 / 100

2.8 Requirements of bitumen

The desirable properties of bitumen depend on the mix type and construction. In general, Bitumen should possess following desirable properties (Amit, 2012).

- The bitumen should not be highly temperature susceptible: during the hottest weather the mix should not become too soft or unstable, and during cold weather the mix should not become too brittle causing cracks.
- The viscosity of the bitumen at the time of mixing and compaction should be adequate. This can be achieved by use of cutbacks or emulsions of suitable grades or by heating the bitumen and aggregates prior to mixing.
- There should be adequate affinity and adhesion between the bitumen and aggregates used in the mix.

2.8.1 The desirable properties of bituminous mixes.

Amit, (2012) also said a good bituminous concrete mix is expected to do the following:

1. Resistance to permanent deformation: The mix should not distort or be displaced when subjected to traffic loads. The resistance to permanent deformation is more important at high temperatures.
2. Fatigue resistance: the mix should not crack when subjected to repeated loads over a period of time.
3. Resistance to low temperature cracking. This mix property is important in cold regions.
4. Durability: the mix should contain sufficient asphalt cement to ensure an adequate film thickness around the aggregate particles. The compacted mix should not have very high air voids, which accelerates the aging process.
5. Resistance to moisture-induced damage.
6. Skid resistance.
7. Workability: the mix must be capable of being placed and compacted with reasonable effort.
8. Low noise and good drainage properties: If the mix is to be used for the surface (wearing) layer of the pavement structure.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The method adopted in this study was divided into four progressive stages as shown in figure 1 and two methods of application of waste plastic to asphalt mixtures were adopted (figure 2).

3.1 Material Characterization and Sourcing

Basic properties of the materials were determined in the laboratory as shown in figure 3 and figure 4 show the materials used in the study as well as their sources.

3.2 Conversion and Application of the Plastics

The PET and LDPE wastes were collected; the unwanted materials were separated and then washed thoroughly in water and allowed to dry naturally. Finally, using a cutter, they were shredded into smaller pieces.

The wastes were used in the following methods:

- (i) Addition (+ ve): Samples were produced with the addition of 1, 3 and 5 % of PET and LDPE waste respectively while the OBC was fixed.
- (ii) Subtraction (- ve): The bitumen within the determined OBC was replaced with PET and LDPE waste in the proportion 1, 3 and 5 %.

Figure 1: Research Method Stages

Figure 2: Methods of application of waste to mixtures

Figure 3: Material Characteristics.

Table 4: Materials and their sources

Material	Source
Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE) - Sachet water Pack	KSM Project Ofada Ogun State, Nigeria. Producers of Babara Pure Water.
Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) - Table water bottle	KSM Project Ofada Ogun State, Nigeria. Producers of Babara Pure Water.
Bitumen Grade: 60/70	EL KARAAN Ltd Papalantoro road, Kajola, Ogun State, Nigeria.
Aggregate	CNC Quarry Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria.

3.3 Determination of Optimum Binder Content

In the Marshall Test method according to AASHTO T166 [AASHTO, 2004(a)] and ASTM D2726 [ASTM, 2004] and ASTM D1559 [ASTM, 2004].

- Three compacted samples were prepared for each binder content.
- Six binder contents (from 5 % to 7.5 %) were tested to get the optimum binder content.
- All the compacted specimens were subjected to the following tests:
 - Bulk density determination.
 - Stability and flow test.
 - Density and voids analysis.
- Five separate smooth curves were drawn with percentage of bitumen on x-axis and the following on y-axis
 - Bulk density (BD)
 - Marshall Stability (MS)
 - Marshall Flow (MF)
 - Voids in Mineral Aggregate (VMA)
 - Voids in total mix (VTM)
- Optimum Binder Content was selected as the average binder content for maximum bulk density, maximum stability and 4 percent void in the total mix.

$$B0 = (B1 + B2 + B3)/3 \qquad 1$$

Where,

B0 = optimum Bitumen content.

B1 = % asphalt content at maximum Bulk Density.

B2 = % asphalt content at maximum stability.

B3 = % asphalt content at 4 percent air voids in the total mix.
(AASHTO T166 [AASHTO, 2004(a)], ASTM D2726 [ASTM, 2004] and ASTM D1559 [ASTM, 2004].)

3.4 Evaluation of the asphalt.

Marshall Specimens each of the Hot Mix Asphalt at pre-determined optimum binder content were produced to reflect various percentages of the shredded PET and LDPE. The specimens were prepared in the laboratory for replacement of OBC with waste plastics and addition of waste plastics to OBC; one specimen at the optimum binder content, unmodified as a control.

The following laboratory tests were carried out on the unmodified and the modified bitumen mixes. The laboratory tests are

- Marshall Stability and flow,
- Density,
- Void in Total Mix, and
- Void filled with bitumen.

3.4.1 Ductility Test (ASTM D113 – 07)

Apparatus:

Briquette mould, (length – 75 mm, distance between clips – 30 mm, width at mouth of clips – 20 mm, cross section at minimum width – 10 mm x 10 mm), Ductility machine with water bath and a pulling device at a pre-calibrated rate, a putty knife, thermometer.

Procedure:

- The bitumen sample is method to a pouring temperature (75 °C to 100 °C) and poured into the mould assembly and placed on a brass plate, where a

solution of glycerin or soap solution is applied at all surfaces of briquette mould exposed to bitumen.

- After the sample is poured to the mould, thirty to forty minutes the entire assembly is placed in a water bath at 27 °C.
- Then the sample is removed from the water bath maintained at 27 °C and excess bitumen material is cut off by leveling the surface using hot knife.
- After trimming the specimen, the mould assembly containing sample is replaced in water bath maintained at 27 °C for 85 to 95 minutes. Then the sides of mould are removed and the clips are carefully booked on the machine without causing any initial strain. Two or more specimens may be prepared in the moulds and clipped to the machine so as to conduct these test simultaneously.
- The pointer is set to read zero. The machine is started and the two clips are thus pulled apart horizontally.
- While the test is in operation, it is checked whether the sample is immersed in water at depth of at least 10 mm. The distance at which the bitumen thread of each specimen breaks is recorded (in mm) to report as ductility value.

3.4.2 Flash and fire point test (ASTM Manual 72 MNL72)

Procedure:

- The bitumen was filled into a dried cup up to a mark. The lid was placed to close the cup in a closed system and thermometer was suitably fixed.
- The bitumen sample was then heated. The heating of sample was done at a rate of about 5 °C to 6 °C per minute.

- During heating, stirring was done at a rate of approximately 60 revolutions per minute.
- The test flame was applied at intervals and corresponding temperatures (at which the material shows the sign of flash and fire) were noted.

3.4.3 Penetration test (ASTM D5/D5M – 13)

Procedure:

- The bitumen was softened to a paving consistency between 60 °C and 70 °C.
- The sample material was thoroughly stirred to make it homogeneous and free from air bubbles and water.
- The sample containers were cooled in atmosphere. Then they were placed in temperature controlled water bath at a temperature of 25 °C for a period of one hour.
- The weight of needle, shaft and additional weight were checked.
- Using the adjusting screw, the needle assembly was lowered and the tip of the needle was made to just touch the top surface of the sample.
- The needle assembly was clamped in this position. The contact of the tip of the needle was checked using the mirror placed on the rear of the needle.
- The initial reading of the penetrometer dial was either adjusted to zero or the initial reading was noted.
- Then the needle was released by pressing a button and a stop watch is started. The needle is released exactly for a period of 5.0 seconds.
- Three measurements were made on this sample by testing at distance of not less than 100 mm apart.

- The difference between the initial and final penetration readings were taken as the penetration value.

3.4.4 Specific Gravity test (ASTM D2041/D2041M - 11)

Procedure:

- The clean, dried specific gravity bottle was weighed let that be W_1 gm.
- Then it was filled with fresh distilled water and then kept in water bath for at least half an hour at temperature $27\text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.
- The bottle was then removed and cleaned from outside. The specific gravity bottle containing distilled water was then weighed. Let this be W_2 gm.
- Then the specific gravity bottle was emptied and cleaned. The material was heated to a pouring temperature and the material was poured half the bottle, by taking care to prevent entry of air bubbles. Then it was weighed. Let this be W_3 gm.
- The remaining space in specific gravity bottle was filled with distilled water at $27\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and weighed. Let this be W_4 gm.

3.5 Specimen preparation ASTM D2726 (ASTM, 2004)

Approximately 1200 gm of aggregates and filler was heated to a temperature of $175 - 190\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Bitumen was also heated to a temperature of $121-190\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with the first trial percentage of bitumen. The heated aggregates and bitumen were thoroughly mixed at a temperature of $154-160\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The mix was placed in a preheated mould and compacted by a rammer with 50 blows on either side at temperature of $138\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $149\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The bitumen content was varied in the next trials by $+ 0.5\%$ and the above procedure repeated.

The hot mix blend of waste LDPE and PET with asphalt mix was achieved by partially replacing the OBC with shredded LDPE and PET plastic waste at 1, 3 and 5 %, weight replacements and addition.

The properties that are of interest include the theoretical specific gravity, the bulk specific gravity of the mix, percent voids in total mix and percent voids filled with bitumen VFB. These calculations were carried out as follows;

Theoretical specific gravity G_t : The specific gravity without considering air voids, and is given by:

$$G_t = \left\{ \frac{W_1+W_2+W_3+W_b}{\left[\frac{W_1}{G_1}\right] + \left[\frac{W_2}{G_2}\right] + \left[\frac{W_3}{G_3}\right] + \left[\frac{W_b}{G_b}\right]} \right\} \quad 2$$

where,

W_1 is the weight of coarse aggregate in the total mix,

W_2 is the weight of fine aggregate in the total mix,

W_3 is the weight of filler in the total mix,

W_b is the weight of bitumen in the total mix,

G_1 is the apparent specific gravity of coarse aggregate,

G_2 is the apparent specific gravity of fine aggregate,

G_3 is the apparent specific gravity of filler and

G_b is the apparent specific gravity of bitumen,

Bulk specific gravity of mix G_m : The bulk specific gravity or the actual specific gravity of the mix G_m is the specific gravity considering air voids and is found out by:

$$G_m = W_m / (W_m - W_w) \quad 3$$

where,

W_m is the weight of mix in air,

W_w is the weight of mix in water,

Note that $(W_m - W_w)$ gives the volume of the mix.

Air voids percent or % void in total mix. V_v : Air voids V_v is the percent of air voids by volume in the specimen and is given by:

$$V_v = [(G_t - G_m)100]/G_t \quad 4$$

Where;

G_t is the theoretical specific gravity of the mix, and

G_m is the bulk or actual specific gravity of the mix.

Voids Filled with Bitumen(VFB). The portion of the voids in the mineral aggregate that contain asphalt binder. This represents the volume of the effective asphalt content.

$$VFB = V_{be}/(V_{be} + V_v) \quad 5$$

Where; $V_T = \text{total volume of compacted specimen}$

$V_a = \text{volume of air void}$

$V_b = \text{volume of binder}$

$V_{be} = \text{volume of effective binder}$

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The objective of the design of bituminous mix is to determine an economical blend through several trial mixes. The gradation of aggregate and the corresponding binder content should be such that the resultant mix should satisfy the following conditions.

- (i) Sufficient binder (OBC) to ensure a durable pavement by providing a water proofing coating on the aggregate particles and binding them together under suitable compaction.
- (ii) Sufficient flexibility to withstand deflection and bending without cracking. to obtain desired flexibility, it is necessary to have proper amount and grade of bitumen (OBC).
- (iii) Sufficient stability (MS) for providing resistance to deformation under sustained or repeated loads. This resistance in the mixture is obtained from aggregate interlocking and cohesion which generally develops due to binder in the mix.
- (iv) Sufficient voids in the total compacted mix (VTM) to provide space for additional compaction under traffic loading.
- (v) Sufficient workability (MF) for an efficient construction operation in laying the paving mixture.

4.2 Material Characterization

The aggregate particle size distribution is shown in figure 1 while table 5 shows the distribution in relation with the Federal Ministry of Works (FMW) standard. The

result of the properties of the bitumen (60 / 70 grade) used relative to the FMW standard is presented in figure 2 and appendix 1.

The results show that the materials were within the acceptable limits as specified by the standard and are therefore suitable for use in asphalt concrete mix production.

Fig.4 Sieve Analysis curve for the aggregate

Table 5: A comparison of sieve analysis test result with FMW standard

SIEVE SIZE	FMW STANDARD		
	Min.	Test Result	Max.
31.8	100	100	100
25	100	100	100
19	100	100	100
12.5	85	100	100
9.5	75	91	92
6.4	65	81	82
2.8	50	60.6	65
1.25	36	44.8	51
0.6	26	35	40
0.3	18	24	30
0.15	13	15	24
0.075	7	4.67	14

Fig 5: Bitumen properties test result against standard

4.3 Determination of Optimum Binder Content

The result of parameters tested/determined for samples with varying content of bitumen (5 to 7.5 %) in order to determine the Optimum Binder Content are presented in Appendix 2. In figures 6 to 10 shows the rate of change of these parameters with increase in bitumen content.

The result shows an increase in value as the bitumen content increases for for percentage VFB but BD and MS increased till a peak is reached and thereafter, the values started decreasing. The result for MF shows an initial drop in value till a peak drop is attained and it begins to rise again. For VTM a consistent decrease was observed as bitumen content increases. The adopted OBC is presented in table 6.

Fig. 6 Bulk Density Vs percentage of bitumen

Fig. 7 Percentage Void in Total Mix Vs Percentage of Bitumen

Fig. 8: Marshal Stability Vs Percentage of Bitumen

Fig.9 : Marshal Flow Vs Percentage of Bitumen

Fig. 10 Percentage Void Filled with Bitumen Vs Percentage of Bitumen

Table 6: The Optimum Binder Content Result

% Bit. Content	Bulk Density	SGM	VTM	VFB	Marshal Stability (kN)	Marshal Flow (mm)
6.6	2.371	2.457	3.5	81.25	16.945	4.2

Note: Maximum Stability = 7 %, Maximum Bulk Density = 6.5 % Bitumen Content,

4 % air void = 6.3 % Bitumen Content. $OBC = (7 + 6.5 + 6.3) / 3 = 6.6\%$

4.4 Evaluation of Asphalt Produced

4.4.1 Standards

Tables 7 and 8 shows the two standards considered in this study; the Asphalt Institute standard and the Federal Ministry of Works standard.

The important parameters are indicated on the table as well as their acceptable limits.

Table 7: Asphalt Institute Standard

Traffic Category	Light		Medium		Heavy	
Compaction, No. of 35 blows/side			50		75	
Stability, (N)	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.
	3333	NA	5333	NA	8000	NA
Flow, (0.25 mm)	8	18	8	16	8	14
Air Voids, (%)	3	5	3	5	3	5
VFB, (%)	65	75	65	78	70	80

Source: Asphalt Institute, 1997.

Table 8: Federal Ministry of Work Standard

Property	Base-course	Wearing-course
Optimum Bitumen Content	4.5 - 6.5 %	5.0 - 8.0 %
Stability, not less than	3.5 KN	3.5 KN
Flow	2 - 6 mm	2 - 4 mm
Air Void	3 - 8 %	3 - 5 %
Voids filled with bitumen (VFB)	65 - 72 %	75 - 82 %

Source: Federal Ministry of Works Nigeria, (1997)

4.4.2 Addition and Subtraction of Plastic waste

Appendix 3 and 4 present the test result of the parameters for LDPE and PET respectively, when plastic waste were added (+ ve) to the determined OBC and when some percentages of OBC were replaced (- ve) with plastic waste.

The reaction of the various parameters to the application of these plastics is as presented in figures 11, 13, 14, 15 and 17. Figures; 12, 16 and 18 shows an evaluation of the result of Marshal Flow, Void in Total Mix and Void Filled with Bitumen respectively with the FMW standard.

Going by the standards and the limits specified, the most acceptable result for LDPE and PET-Modified Asphalt concrete mix is presented on table 14.

Fig. 11: Changes in MF with Percentage of LDPE/PET to OBC

Fig. 12 MF Vs Standard

Fig. 13: Changes in MS with Percentage of LDPE/PET to OBC

Fig. 14: Changes in BD with Percentage of LDPE/PET to OBC

Fig. 15: Changes in VTM with Percentage of LDPE/PET to OBC

Fig. 16: Changes in Percentage VTM Vs FMW Standard

Fig. 17: Changes in VFB with Percentage of LDPE/PET to OBC

Fig. 18: Changes in Percentage VFB Vs FMW Standard

4.5 COST ANALYSIS

4.5.1 Assumptions

The assumption, estimations and cost analysis are presented on table 9, 10 and 12 respectively. The result of this analysis indicates that LDPE – Modified Asphalt will cost less (7.9 %) to produce while PET – Modified Asphalt will cost a little more (0.9 %) compared to the Unmodified Asphalt.

Table 9: Assumptions for cost analysis

S/No.	Item	Qty
1	Assumed Road Length (m)	1,000.000
2	Assumed Road Width (m)	7.300
3	Assumed Thickness of Asphalt Paving (m)	0.050
4	Volumn (m ³)	365.000
5	Density of Asphalt Paving (g / cm ³)	2.371
	Density of Asphalt Paving (kg / m ³)	2,371.000
6	Mass (kg)	865,415.000
	Mass (Tons)	953.957

Table 10: Estimations based on assumptions

Materials	Rate (Naira/ton)	Estimated Cost (Naira)
Asphalt (EL KARAAN Ltd)	19,000.00	18,125,178.10
Bitumen (EL KARAAN Ltd)	175,000.00	11,018,200.37
Aggregate (CNC Quarry)	7,980.00	7,110,144.87

Table 11: Most Acceptable Result

Modifier	% Bitumen Content	Bulk Density	SGM	VTM	VFB	Marshal Stability (kN)	Marshal Flow (mm)
LDPE (Waste Sachet Water Pack)	-1	2.39	4.06	17.21	27.75	3.82	2.39
PET (Waste Table Water Bottle)	1	2.376	2.437	3.327	82.21	17.01	4

Table 12: Cost analysis

Description Materials	Unit	Rate	Control Mix		Modified Mix (LDPE)		Modified Mix (PET)	
			Qty	Amount (N)	Qty	Amount (N)	Qty	Amount (N)
Aggregate	Tons	7,980.00	890.996	7,110,144.87	890.996	7,110,144.87	881.456	7,034,019.12
Bitumen	Tons	175,000.00	62.961	11,018,200.37	53.422	9,348,776.07	62.961	11,018,200.37
Plastic	Tons	25,000.00			9.540	238,489.19	9.540	238,489.19
Total				18,128,345.24		16,697,410.13		18,290,708.68
% Difference						7.89		-0.90
Cost Difference						1,430,935.11		(162,363.44)

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSIONS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 DISCUSSION

The problems of sanitation and contamination can be traced to the environmental and water contamination by waste generation (David, 2012). The World today is facing a waste crisis from the plastic usage (Greenpeace, 2011) which is estimated at about 7 % of the Municipal Solid Waste (Amit *et al.*, 2012).). The per capita per year consumption of plastic is estimated at 24 to 28 kg (Amit *et al.*, 2012).) of which Nigeria generates 990.344 Km² daily (David, 2012). The economic, health and environmental implications of this non-degradable waste (plastic) necessitates the need for researches geared towards tackling this looming danger. This study in an attempt to find a lasting solution to this danger, investigated the feasibility of the use of the two major plastic wastes in Nigeria (Sachet Water Pack – LDPE and Table Water Bottle – PET).

A comparative study of asphalt mix was carried out to find the effect of replacing bitumen by adding plastic (LDPE & PET) waste and the effect when a predetermined Optimum Binder Content is retained and plastic (LDPE & PET) waste were added to the mix. The Waste Plastic-Modified Asphalt mix samples were subjected to Marshall Stability and Marshall Flow tests. Bulk Density, Void in Total Mix, and Void Filled with Bitumen were determined and the results evaluated with reference to standards.

Aggregate gradation is the distribution of particle sizes expressed as a percentage of the total weight and is determined by sieve analysis (Abukhettala, 2006). Properties of Hot-mix asphalt mixture like stiffness, stability, durability, fatigue resistance and resistance to permanent deformation, are largely affected by aggregate gradation, it is

therefore, considered the most important property of aggregate that influences the performance of asphalt concrete (Abukhettala, 2006). In this study, the aggregate gradation based on the sieve analysis result is found suitable and the bitumen (60 / 70 grade) used also satisfied the requirements of a good binder material.

Suitably designed bituminous mix will withstand heavy traffic loads under adverse climatic conditions and also fulfill the requirement of structural and pavement surface characteristics (Bindu, 2012). There are three principal bituminous mix design methods in general use; Marshall, Hveem and Superpave methods, but Marshall Mix Design Method is the widely used method (Bindu, 2012) and it is the design method adopted for this research. Fundamentally, mix design is meant to determine the volume of bitumen binder and aggregates necessary to produce a mixture with the desired properties (Abukhettala, 2006). Putting this method to use, a mix design with 6.6 % of bitumen by weight of aggregate offered the most desirous properties and therefore was adopted as the control.

Stability is the load that a well-compacted paving mixture can accept and withstand before failure (Abukhettala, 2006). Therefore stability is required to meet the demands of traffic without rutting or bleeding. The study results shows that the modification of HMA with plastic effectively improves the stability values, resulting in an improved toughness and therefore a better performance compared with the control mix.

LDPE offers a better stability in almost all cases while PET provides a better mix only with a 1% addition of the plastic to the OBC. In both cases it was obvious that as the plastic content increases, the stability of the mix reduces. This is an indication that excessive addition of plastic may not disperse uniformly and may cluster together to form weak point within the mixture hence the loss of stability.

Comparing the two types of plastics LDPE offers the highest stability of 27.75 KN at 1 % replacement of OBC. This indicates that LDPE has a higher rutting resistance and thus better performance compared to PET. The percentage increase in stability with respect to the control mixture is about 64 % for LDPE and about 1 % for PET. Considering the specification, the two plastics offered an acceptable stability in all cases examined. These indicate that the various modifications can find applicability in one form or the other provided other parameters are satisfied.

The binder content (bitumen + plastic) holds the aggregates in position, and the load is taken by the aggregate mass through the contact points but if all the voids are filled with the binder, the stone to stone contact of the aggregate particles may be lost, and then the load is transmitted by hydrostatic pressure through the binder, hence the strength of the mix reduces (Bindu, 2012). That is why stability of the mix starts reducing when binder is increased beyond a certain value.

Marshal flow result from the study ranged between 5.37 and 3.82 mm for LDPE with a 27 % increase from the result for the control mixture and between 12.5 and 4.0 mm for PET with a 197 % increase compared to the control mixture. This indicates the PET samples are more workable compared to the LDPE samples and also show low resistance to deformation as a result of the reduction in stone – to – stone contact within the samples. The FMW standards permit flow within the range of 2 – 4 mm which all the modification for LDPE met for both base and wearing course but for PET, 1 % replacement of OBC and 1 and 3 % addition to OBC meet the standard.

The two standards considered in this study specifies that VFB should be within the range of 65 – 72 % - (base course light & medium traffic) and 75 – 82 % (wearing course heavy traffic) respectively. But in the modifications with PET, 1 and 3 % addition to OBC satisfies the wearing course/heavy traffic category requirement and 1,

3 & 5 % replacement of OBC satisfies the requirement for LPDE as well. 1.2 % increase was observed for PET at 1 % addition to OBC relative to the control sample's result but there was a 13.5 % increase for LDPE. The decrease of VFB indicates a decrease of effective bitumen film thickness between aggregates, which will result in higher low-temperature cracking and lower durability of bitumen mixture since bitumen perform the filling and healing effects to improve the flexibility of mixture (Bindu, 2012).

The result shows that the more plastic is added to the mix, the lesser the VFB value for PET when the OBC is retained. It also shows that the more the bitumen is replaced with the plastic the lesser the value of VFB. The trend is same for LDPE on the replacement of OBC side of the graph but on the addition of LDPE when OBC is retained there was a consistent increase in VFB, indicating that LDPE dissolved more readily to fill more void with increased bitumen content than when the bitumen is reduce than PET. Nevertheless, this parameter helps to further determine the more appropriate options (mix designs) to adopt.

During dry season, bitumen softens and occupies the void space between the aggregates and if void is unavailable, bleeding is caused, and thus some amount of void is necessary in a bituminous mix, even after the final stage of compaction. However excess void will make the mix weak from its elastic modulus and fatigue life considerations, therefore amount of air voids in a mixture is extremely important and closely related to stability, durability and permeability (Bindu, 2012).

The results in this research indicates that there is a consistent increase in VTM as the quantity of plastic (PET) used increases. LDPE shows a drop in VTM with increased use of the plastic. Based on the specifications, 1 % replacement of OBC and 1 & 3 %

additions to OBC meets the specification for PET while only 1 and 3 % replacement of OBC meets the standard in the case of LDPE.

The result restricts the application of LDPE as modifier to 1 and 3% replacement of OBC as well as 1 % replacement and 1 and 3 % addition, for PET as far as VTM is concerned.

The cost analysis shows a 7.37 % cost reduction in the case of waste LDPE and a 0.90 % cost increase in the case of waste PET. If this analysis is done on a larger scale it is most likely that the cost in the case of PET will reduce.

Nevertheless, if a cost comparison of the effect of the indiscriminate dumping of waste PET plastic is done as against the cost increase obtained above it is likely to further show that this approach is more economical.

5.3 CONCLUSION

Based on the parameters obtained from the tests, the Optimum Binder Content (OBC) was found to be 6.6 % by wt. of aggregates which was used to evaluate the effect of different percentage of modifiers on the strength and performance characteristics of different mixtures. The result of the evaluation showed that the maximum allowable LDPE waste modification was found to be 1 % (replacement of OBC) by weight of aggregate (15 % by weight of bitumen) and the modification was adequate in raising the stability of the asphalt mix from 16.95 to 27.75 kN. So also, the maximum allowable PET waste modification was found to be 1 % (addition to OBC) by weight of aggregate (15 % by weight of bitumen) which was also adequate in raising the stability of the asphalt mix to 17 kN. The cost analysis also showed a 7.37 % cost reduction in the case of waste LDPE and a 0.90 % cost increase in the case of waste PET.

Going by all these, it could be concluded that the waste plastic modified asphalt mix forms better material for pavement construction as the mix shows higher Marshall Stability value, suitable percentage void in total mix, acceptable percentage of voids filled with bitumen with Marshall Flow within standard specified range. Furthermore, the cost implications of these modifications are better compared to the environmental hazards from their disposal (landfill and / or incineration). Hence the use of waste plastics for pavement is one of the most effective and economical methods for easy disposal of plastics waste.

5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommended:

- i. further research work should be done in this regard to ascertain the possible health hazard associate with the industrial processes involved in this modification considering the carcinogenic nature of plastics.
- ii. government/private organizations should fund a large scale application of the findings of this study for actualization and possible legislation.
- iii. Nigerian government should start to make effort to reduce plastic waste generation in the country through the promotion of the 3Rs Concept as obtainable elsewhere to forestall the looming dangers there-in.
- iv. Legislation and enforcement are critically required on the part of Government.

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PLATES

Plate 1: A Dumpsite at RCG Camp along Lagos Ibadan Express way

Plate 2: A Dumpsite around Mowe / Ibafo Area Ogun State

Plate 3: Cat-Pushers' dumpsite of Plastic waste

Plate 4: Plastic bottles flooding drain

Plate 5: LDPE Modified Asphalt Samples

Plate 6: Penetration Test

Plate 7: Sample Labelling

Plate 8: Sample undergoing Marshall Stability and Flow Test

APPENDIXES

APPENDIX 1: A graphical comparison of sieve analysis test result versus FMW Standard

APPENDIX 2: Properties test result for the bitumen.

Asphalt Cement Property	Test Result	Standard (60 – 70 PEN)
Specific Gravity @ 25°C	1.02	1.01 – 1.06
Softening Point R and B (°C)	50	48 – 56
Penetration @ 25°C – 0.1mm	68	60 – 70
Ductility @ 25°C – cm (Minimum)	120	100
Flash Point (open cup) °C (Minimum)	280	250

APPENDICE 3: Test result to determine OBC

% Bit. Cont.	Bulk Density	SGM	VTM	VFB	Marshal Stability	Marshal Flow
5	2.33	2.52	7.4	60.60	16.685	4.96
5.5	2.35	2.50	6.1	67.31	16.72	4.2
6	2.36	2.48	4.9	74.00	16.78	3.8
6.5	2.37	2.46	3.7	80.33	16.93	3.91
7	2.37	2.44	3.1	84.10	16.97	6.8
7.5	2.36	2.43	2.5	87.38	16.85	8.37

Appendix 4: Addition and Subtraction of LPDE to Optimum Binder Content

% (+ / -) LPDE	Bulk Density g / cm ³	VTM %	VFB %	Marshal Stability (KN)	Marshal Flow (mm)
-5	2.61	1.68	70.91	14.22	4.11
-3	2.5	2.9	75.28	18.02	3.83
-1	2.39	4.06	76.4	27.75	3.82
0	2.37	3.54	81.25	16.95	4.2
1	2.41	1.99	88.68	24.74	4.07
3	2.43	1.32	92.23	20.68	4.59
5	2.41	1.96	88.81	17.15	5.37

Appendix 5: Addition and Subtraction of PET to Optimum Binder Content

% (+ / -) PET	Bulk Density g / cm ³	VTM %	VFB %	Marshal Stability (KN)	Marshal Flow (mm)
-5	2.158	18.836	15.233	4.000	12.500
-3	2.206	14.324	35.212	9.750	7.600
-1	2.341	6.202	67.449	15.520	4.800
0	2.370	3.541	81.249	16.945	4.200
1	2.376	3.327	82.209	17.010	4.000
3	2.344	4.649	76.537	10.730	5.560
5	1.950	20.668	37.907	7.200	9.250